

APPLICATION OF HAMMICK AND ANDREW'S EQUATION TO TERNARY MIXTURES. PART III.

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Hammick and Andrew's equation is applicable to ternary mixtures of glucose, urea and acetamide in water. The values are compared with those obtained in aqueous solution and not with the calculated values. It is observed that for binary mixtures the values obtained for solids are generally much lower than those obtained by calculations.

For determining the parachors of binary and ternary mixtures the formulae

$$P_m = (1-x) P_p + x P_x \text{ and}$$

$$P_m = (1-x-y) P_p + x P_x + y P_y$$

respectively are employed; where P_m , P_x , P_y , P_p and x have their usual significance.

In previous papers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 21, 179; 1945, 22, 311) it was shown that the mixture law of determining parachor was applicable to ternary mixtures. The work has been extended in this paper.

Parachor of Glucose

TABLE I

Temp.	4.8042 G. of glucose dissolved in 14.7023 g. of water. x (glucose) = 0.0321; $1-x$ (water) = 0.9679; $M_m = 23.21$.				3.5920 G. of glucose dissolved in 14.8654 g. of water. $x = 0.0235$; $1-x$ (water) = 0.9765; $M_m = 21.82$.			
	d .	r .	P_m .	P_x .	d .	r .	P_m .	P_x .
20°	1.100	73.67	61.8	347.0	1.073	71.76	59.2	344.3
30	1.097	72.44	61.72	344.6	1.071	70.99	59.15	342.0
40	1.093	71.78	61.81	347.3	1.067	69.98	59.14	341.7
50	1.080	70.79	61.77	346.1	1.064	69.18	59.14	341.7

Calc. value = 377.2

Temp.	5.5812 G. of glucose dissolved in 14.9040 g. of water. $x = 0.0361$; $1-x = 0.9639$; $M_m = 23.84$.				2.8292 G. of glucose dissolved in 14.295 g. of water. $x = 0.0193$; $1-x = 0.9807$; $M_m = 21.14$.			
	d .	r .	P_m .	P_x .	d .	r .	P_m .	P_x .
25°	1.110	73.75	62.94	346.9	1.083	71.86	57.91	340.9
30	1.107	72.44	62.85	343.4	1.061	71.29	57.89	339.9
40	1.103	71.61	62.83	344.3	1.058	70.91	57.86	338.3
50	1.100	70.63	62.84	343.2	1.054	69.18	57.84	337.3

Parachor of Urea

There seems to be some discrepancy in the values recorded by us in our previous paper for the parachor of urea (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 21, 179). The revised results are recorded below.

TABLE II

5.4378 G. of urea dissolved in 14.8954 g. of water. x (urea) = 0.996; $1-x$ = 0.9014; $M_m = 22.07$.				7.0282 G. of urea dissolved in 14.7036 g. of water. $x = 0.1263$; $1-x = 0.8747$; $M_m = 23.27$.				
Temp.	d .	r .	P_m .	P_x .	d .	r .	P_m .	P_x .
26°	1.070	72.04	60.09	130.9	1.067	71.69	62.15	130.6
30	1.067	70.79	59.99	128.9	1.055	70.70	62.2	131.0
40	1.063	69.98	60.06	130.5	1.062	70.15	62.24	131.3
50	1.057	69.67	60.15	131.5	1.076	68.67	62.18	130.8

Calc. value = 141.2

8.7788 G. of urea dissolved in 15.0086 g. of water. $x = 0.1493$; $1-x = 0.8507$; $M_m = 24.37$					
Temp.	d .	r .	P_m .	P_x .	
26°	1.101	71.39	64.6	130.8	
30	1.099	70.47	64.01	130.6	
40	1.094	69.18	63.96	130.1	
50	1.090	67.76	63.84	129.1	

The work of Hammick and Andrew (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 754) for binary mixtures includes only liquid-liquid mixtures, where the agreement between the calculated and the observed values is excellent. Our work with solid-liquid mixtures (*loc. cit.*) shows that the values obtained in solution for solids (non-electrolytes) are generally smaller than the calculated values. These observations for solid-liquid system are similar to those of Hammick and Andrew (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 33) in case of tetranitromethane in benzene and to those of Ray (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 845; 1935, 12, 407) in case of fructose in various solvents. In applying therefore the equation for ternary mixture, we have not used the calculated values, but the actual values obtained for these solids in water. The agreement between these results and those obtained by ternary expression is excellent. This will be clear from the following results.

Urea and glucose may have the following structures.

The values obtained in each case are lower than the corresponding set of values given by the above structures. Clearly the observed values approach that structure whose calculated values are lower. But since the values in water are in general smaller, it will not be justified to say that the structure of glucose or urea corresponds to that formula which gives smaller value on calculations.

TABLE III

Glucose, acetamide and water system.

3.470 G. of glucose and 7.2552 g. of acetamide dissolved in 7.3983 g. of water. x (glucose) = 0.0230; y (acetamide) = 0.3223; $1-x-y$ (water) = 0.7537; $M_m = 81.20$. Parachor of water as determined = 52.34; parachor of acetamide = 135.

Temp.	d .	r .	P_m .	P_x .
25°	1.067	53.2	77.54	346.7
30°	1.065	52.48	77.39	340.2
40°	1.061	52.0	77.52	345.8
50°	1.078	51.29	77.45	342.8

Glucose (2.8756g.) and acetamide (5.3210g.) dissolved in 7.4583 g. of water. x (glucose) = 0.0295; y (acetamide) = 0.1785 $1-x-y$ (water) = 0.7980; $M_m = 29.76$.

d .	r .	P_m .	P_x .
1.062	57.49	75.06	346.4
1.060	56.62	75.0	344.0
1.067	56.34	75.11	348.5
1.063	53.7	75.08	347.0

4.9380 G. of glucose and 10.5482 g. of acetamide dissolved in 15.0088 g. of water. x (glucose) = 0.02816; y (acetamide) = 0.1719; $1-x-y$ (water) = 0.80194; $M_m = 29.30$.

Temp.	d .	r .	P_m .	P_x .
25°	1.067	56.86	74.11	340.2
30°	1.065	56.23	73.93	335.2
40°	1.062	55.72	73.82	331.0
50°	1.078	54.95	73.99	337.5

5.3212 G. of acetamide and 1.7916 g. of glucose dissolved in 7.6984 g. of water. x (acetamide) = 0.1701; y (glucose) = 0.0189; $1-x-y$ (water) = 0.8110; $M_m = 28.24$.

d .	r .	P_m .	P_x .
1.071	56.78	72.28	186.2
1.068	55.95	72.11	135.8
1.065	54.95	72.11	186.9
1.060	53.83	72.14	186.0

7.9982 G. of acetamide and 1.7974 g. of glucose dissolved in 7.4424 g. of water.

Temp.	d .	r .
25°	1.069	51.88
30°	1.066	51.11
40°	1.062	50.12
50°	1.058	49.2

x (acetamide) = 0.2395; y (glucose) = 0.0177; $1-x-y$ (water) = 0.7428; $M_m = 29.97$

P_m .	P_x .
77.8	136.6
77.69	136.1
77.43	135.0
77.54	135.5

TABLE IV

Urea, glucose and water system.

5.4694 G. of urea and 4.8648 g. of glucose dissolved in 14.9054 g. of water. x (urea) = 0.09828; y (glucose) = 0.02853; $1-x-y$ (water) = 0.87619; $M_m = 28.68$.

Temp.	d .	r .	P_m .	P_x .
25°	1.140	72.98	68.38	131.6
30°	1.138	72.11	68.32	130.9
40°	1.135	71.45	68.34	131.1
50°	1.131	70.79	68.40	132.0

7.0774 G. of urea and 4.9294 g. of glucose dissolved in 14.9832 g. of water. x (urea) = 0.1207; y (glucose) = 0.02805; $1-x-y$ (water) = 0.8513; $M_m = 27.61$.

d .	r .	P_m .	P_x .
1.149	72.71	70.16	132.7
1.147	71.79	70.08	130.8
1.144	70.79	70.01	130.2
1.141	70.15	70.08	130.4

TABLE IV (contd.)

7.7750 G. of urea and 4.9796 g. of glucose dissolved in 13.9140 g. of water. w (urea) = 0.1392 ; y (glucose) = 0.0297 ; $1-x-y$ (water) = 0.8311 ; $M_m = 28.85$.					4.2696 G. of urea and 4.8738 g. of glucose dissolved in 14.9156 g. of water. x (urea) = 0.7686 ; y (glucose) = 0.02918 ; $1-x-y$ (water) = 0.89416 ; $M_m = 28.88$.				
	Temp.	d .	P_m .	P_x .		Temp.	d .	P_m .	P_x .
	25°	1.169	74.01	72.51	134.3	1.133	72.98	68.89	129.8
	30	1.166	72.98	72.43	133.0	1.130	72.11	68.86	129.4
	40	1.164	71.78	72.28	132.7	1.127	71.29	68.70	128.1
	60	1.160	70.79	72.28	132.7	1.123	70.15	68.63	129.0
7.1090 G. of urea and 3.5556 g. of glucose dissolved in 14.9388 g. of water. w (urea) = 0.1224 ; y (glucose) = 0.0203 ; $1-x-y$ (water) = 0.8573 ; $M_m = 28.44$.					8.7266 G. of urea and 3.5802 g. of glucose dissolved in 14.9378 g. of water. x (urea) = 0.1463 ; y (glucose) = 0.0200 ; $1-x-y$ (water) = 0.8337 ; $M_m = 27.39$				
	26°	1.182	71.47	67.89	130.5	1.144	73.13	70.01	132.6
	30	1.139	70.47	67.67	130.3	1.142	72.11	69.88	131.9
	40	1.128	69.18	67.79	129.5	1.138	70.79	69.82	131.5
	50	1.120	67.76	67.74	129.2	1.133	69.34	69.78	131.1
4.2864 G. of urea and 3.5928 g. of glucose dissolved in 14.8706 g. of water. x (urea) = 0.0778 ; y (glucose) = 0.0316 ; $y = 0.0316$; $1-x-y$ (water) = 0.9006 ; $M_m = 24.79$.					5.4532 G. of urea and 3.5946 g. of glucose dissolved in 14.9868 g. of water. x (urea) = 0.0963 ; y (glucose) = 0.0211 ; $1-x-y$ (water) = 0.8826 ; $M_m = 25.47$.				
	28°	1.116	71.79	64.54	127.3	1.122	72.4	68.21	131.8
	30	1.114	70.15	64.42	125.8	1.120	69.5	68.66	126.1
	40	1.111	69.18	64.36	125.0	1.117	68.55	68.63	125.8
	50	1.107	67.92	64.31	124.4	1.112	67.61	68.67	126.2

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